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Guidance and Counseling Services: An Instrument for Curbing Indiscipline among Students in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This paper Examined Guidance and Counselling Services: An Instrument for Curbing indiscipline among Students in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Guidance is advice or relevant information provided by a superior to resolve a problem or overcome difficulty. Counselling is professional services given to an individual by a counsellor to assist him in overcoming personal or psychological problems. Guidance and counselling are inextricably linked concepts, with one dictating the availability and effectiveness of the other. Guidance services assist students in making the most of the opportunities available to them. All educational activities and services aimed at assisting individual students in understanding themselves and adjusting to school life are included in guidance. Counselling is a one-on-one meeting designed to discuss and understand issues, make suggestions, and empower someone to make decisions about his or her career or life goals. As a result, based on the forgoing the paper takes a look at the concept of guidance and counselling, Guidance and counselling services, Indiscipline among students, Importance of discipline in schools, why indiscipline in schools? Benefits of Curbing indiscipline in schools, Guidance and counselling as an instrument for curbing indiscipline among students. It was concluded that Nigeria's educational system has been plagued with drug abuse, addiction, irresponsible sexual behaviours, and other forms of violence are all on the rise due to indiscipline. The study therefore, recommended among others that Ministry of Education should strengthen guidance counsellors to every public school, facilitate their training and provide the necessary resources to enable them perform their duties effectively.

Keywords: Curbing, Counselling Services, Discipline, Guidance, Indiscipline, Instrument, Indiscipline, Public, Secondary School, Students

INTRODUCTION

A basic component of the educational system, discipline is essential to maintaining pupils' moral principles. Its goals are to restrain, manage, and reroute conduct. Before disciplinary action is taken in a school system, all pupils must be informed of the regulations (Franken, 2021). A very old custom that may date back to the dawn of human history includes discipline. According to Mayer (2021), students' lack of discipline in schools has led to a number of issues, including drug abuse, sexual abuse, killing, and property destruction. Mayer also stated that disciplinary problems in schools and institutions are perhaps the single biggest cause of concern for educators worldwide. There are a number of concerning problems with Nigeria's educational system. Problems such as drug misuse, addictions, careless sexual conduct, and other types of violence are becoming more prevalent. The general trend in school discipline has increased. It appears that the instructor is violating human rights in trying to control the situation. The Ministry of Education has developed a policy on techniques for

guiding and counselling pupils in order to control their conduct in class. Parents and the general public are weeping for their neglected children. The teachers and council members appear to be the most qualified to save them. Canes and other physical punishment have been outlawed by the authorities in schools. The Ministry of Education has recently assigned the teacher counsellor full responsibility for all disciplinary matters (Mayer, 2021).

Guidance and Counselling are two concepts that are inextricably linked, and one dictates the other's availability and effectiveness. Guidance according to Olayinka (2020) defined it as one of the services that help individual to take full advantage of opportunities around them. Guidance according to Osher (2015) encompasses all educational activities and services aimed at supporting individual pupils in understanding themselves and adjusting to school life. Durojaiye (2019) on the other hand, described guidance as a complex process which encompasses the total needs of the individuals to be directed or guided.

All stakeholders are now concerned about cases of indiscipline in public secondary schools in the past few years. According to information gathered by the Education Office in 2014, there have been significant cases of indiscipline in over ten schools over the past three years. These cases have harmed students and teachers, destroyed resources of unknown value, and negatively impacted academic performance. Students conduct taskforce (2021) acknowledged the use of advice and counselling services to address indiscipline. The issues that remain in search of an answer is if counselling and guidance services can accomplish it all alone whether it is suitable in an atmosphere where instances of misconduct are on the rise.

The idea of balancing advice and counselling with punishment aids in determining the importance of these services for students in educational settings. In order to preserve good discipline among students, parents and schools work together to promote principles and standards that, in our opinion, will assist young people in developing strong behavioural norms for the rest of their life. Despite the Ministry of Education's best efforts, there are still recorded incidences of punishment in public secondary schools. The ministry provides assistance and counselling to schools (Idowu, 2014)

Concept of Guidance and Counselling

Guidance as a concept, originated from the word "*guide*" which means to lead, to direct, to care, to instruct, to assist, to manage, to pilot, etc. therefore, it is a process of assisting an individual or group of persons to understand himself or themselves and their environment (Idowu, 2014). Guidance has some services which are aimed at helping the individual to know themselves and their world. Salami (2018) alluded that the formal steps the school takes to make guidance operational and accessible to individuals are known as guidance services.

According to Mutie and Ndambuki (2014) counselling is a procedure that is focused on learning and conducted in an interactive manner with the intention of helping the learner learn more about himself or herself. Olayinka (2013) defined counselling as the process by which one person assist another in fact to face communication. In effect, an adjusted professional and one or more maladjusted individuals engage in a personalised professional engagement known as counselling. Restoring the unadjusted person to emotional or psychological balance is the professional goal of a therapeutic partnership. Professional assistance could take several forms such as education, career, social, entertainment, emotional or moral. From this narrative and as endangering in professional service rendered by professionals in the field of counselling, the contention in literature is that counselling can be seen as part or core of guidance service.

Counselling is a learning-oriented process that usually occur in interactive relationship. The purpose is to help people learn more (self and others). Additional information about situation and events related to a given problem and condition and learn to make this understanding an effective member of society. Counselling is a procedure whereby counsellors demonstrate empathy and care for the individual in question in order to support their growth and positive transformation via self-awareness (Okumu, 2020). The relationship between the individual in need and the concerned party is referred to as counselling. Typically, this is a person-to-person relationship. Though more than two persons may occasionally be involved. It attempts to assist individuals in comprehending and expressing their opinions or living spaces, as well as learning how to reach their objectives by making purposeful, knowledgeable decisions and resolving interpersonal or emotional issues.

In the guidance process, the emphasis is to listening to the problem and the expert will give a solution to the problem. Counselling is designed to discuss and understand issues, suggest and empower someone to make decisions about his/her career of life goal in a one – on – one meeting. As a result, guidance and counselling are aimed at maximizing individual and social growth and self-realization of human potential. In a school setting, students may realise their full potential by aligning their principles, interests, and talents with the program's assistance. It helps kids make wise academic and professional decisions, resolve behavioural, educational, social, and psychological problems, and adjust to normal school life (Gerardo 2016). Because of the importance of academic performance in schools, guidance and counselling services are introduced into the school system to improve the senior secondary school students' performance.

Guidance and Counselling Services in the School

The following are guidance and Counselling services as outlined by Denga (2019):

- **Appraisal service:** It is intended to gather, examine, and apply various goals and subjective intimate, psychological, and social facts on every individual in order to improve people's knowledge of one another and help them understand themselves.
- **Counselling service:** aimed to promote self-awareness and self-improvement through one-on-one or small-group interactions. It is designed to assist individuals in making self-analysis using their capabilities, achievements, interest, and personality traits as criteria for taking actions and decisions.
- **Information Service:** It aims to give people greater information about education, careers, and personal and social prospects so they may make more educated decisions.
- **Planning and placement service:** which aimed at enhancing the development of people to achieve admission into a school of their choice, to get employment in the outside labour market or to get appropriate treatment for any ailment.
- **Follow up, research and evaluation service:** which is designed to help provide information about the effectiveness of the school guidance programme that may warrant the introduction of new methods of teaching or counselling.
- **Orientation service:** which aimed to help individual adjust to the environment of their school, home or community.
- **Referral service:** which helps individuals in setting the best service available in the local environment.
- **Counselling** is a supportive procedure that calls for mental trust, comprehension, discretion, empathy, and rapport.

Indiscipline among Students

Students' lack of discipline or lack of self-control is having an impact on society. Students frequently engage in harsh language, show disdain for their professors, engage in free-form fighting inside schools, insist on copying exam answers, engage in ragging, go on student strikes, and other behaviours. It appears like a bleak future (Gerardo, 2016). Regrettably, it is unfortunate that today's youngsters squander their limited time on irresponsible behaviour. But the increasing lack of discipline cannot be solely attributed to the kids. Numerous other factors can contribute to indiscipline, such as parental neglect, peer or friend pressure, a lack of values in education, the absence of a positive role model, and a flawed educational system that places an excessive amount of emphasis on finishing textbooks within the allotted time. Teachers simply quit providing moral instruction to their students because they are under pressure to finish their textbooks. Character development thus takes a backseat, and students who use electronic devices excessively—such as spending all day on computers and phones playing games or doing pointless work—are also physically unsuitable. The worst part of this issue is that political leaders frequently mislead people and use them as their instruments to sow disarray. It is essential to shield students from the filthy lifestyle of urban areas. Any nation's future lies with its youth. Everything in excess is harmful. An unruly student can ruin their future. Lack of self-control, contempt for parents and other authority figures, ignorance of proper behaviour, selfishness, unpleasantness, and unhappiness, as well as a lack of empathy, patience, and the capacity to share and form friendships, are all consequences of student indiscipline. Additionally, they

are more prone to act negatively and hurt both themselves and other people. Hence, The overhaul of our nation's educational system is a considerably larger issue than the problem of student dissatisfaction and indiscipline (Okumu, 2020). However, what steps can be taken? The system must be completely redesigned to meet modern demands and the lifestyle of India. To handle the problem, one might employ moral teaching, parental direction and strictness, having a decent role model, and many other strategies. "Spare the rod and spoil the child" is a common saying.

Discipline in Schools

Teachers and students are obligated to follow a set of rules in schools known as discipline, and they must do so or face consequences for breaking them. School regulations are essential to laying the foundation for young brains' social behaviour; discipline establishes these limits and directions for pupils. The government typically establishes the majority of these regulations (Okumu, 2020). The Ministry of Education supplies schools with certain essential principles, but schools also have the authority to establish their own policies and sanctions for noncompliance based on international norms and official government recommendations. These guidelines might cover topics like social behaviour, work ethic, dress code, timekeeping, and school timetable, among others. Students should get the foundational education needed to lead successful, independent lives from their schools. Disruptions in the classroom hinder students' progress. Maintaining discipline is essential for educators and administrators to establish a productive learning environment. The most effective strategy for maintaining discipline in the classroom is usually a mix of techniques used consistently and fairly.

Importance of Discipline in Schools

While many schools struggle with discipline, it is essential for kids to make significant academic progress. One advantage of picking a boarding school is that boarding schools have stricter rules about behaviour. A closer examination of the value of discipline in the classroom is provided here.

It is stated by Braddock (2020). While many schools struggle with discipline, it is essential for pupils to meet their academic objectives. One advantage of picking a boarding school is that boarding schools have stricter rules about behaviour. Discipline is essential to schools' efforts to keep pupils safe and on task. Good school discipline techniques support kids in making informed decisions and maintaining their academic focus. Discipline is one of the main causes for which parents enrol their kids in private schools. Concerns about their children attending big classrooms where teachers spend a lot of time with behaviour problems have increased among parents. We don't want our kids to learn in that kind of atmosphere. We want them to attend school so they may learn in a secure and encouraging setting. Examine the ways in which private schools, regardless of level, manage discipline. Since every private school is a separate entity, the policies will differ from one to the next. As you assess which private school is best for your child, be prepared to enquire in-depth regarding discipline.

Four Ways Effective School Discipline Benefits Students as highlighted by Denga (Okumu, 2020)

1. Encourages Positive Academic Performance

The fact that discipline in the classroom improves academic achievement is one of the main arguments in favour of giving it high importance. Academic testing results are often higher for students who understand they are responsible for their behaviour both inside and outside of the classroom. Classroom management reduces distractions and enhances the flow of information while assisting students in staying focused on the teacher's lesson.

2. Helps Students Stay More Focused on Their Goals

Maintaining order in the classroom aids in students' ability to concentrate on their studies. This gradually teaches kids alternative methods of concentration. A well-behaved student may maintain goal focus and make work a high priority. Students who have this concentration are better able to sustain high standards in all facets of their lives outside of the classroom.

3. Limits Problems with Negative Peer Pressure

Peer pressure may have both beneficial and bad effects on a student's life, but having rules in place at school helps lessen the negative effects that children may experience from their peers. When all

students are held to a high level, they are less likely to pressure their peers to make bad decisions. Peer pressure, therefore, is the responsibility to perform and be better.

4. Creates a Safe Environment for Students

The sense of safety that discipline in schools fosters is another advantage. This is especially evident in boarding school settings, when pupils attend classes and reside in one location. Everyone can study in a secure and encouraging atmosphere when there is a clear discipline code in place that both teachers and students can understand and embrace. The advantages of a structured atmosphere are among the factors that lead several families to contemplate sending their children to a boarding school. A good boarding school must have strict rules and regulations, and staff members are always keeping an eye on the children. In a boarding school, students are free to concentrate on their academic performance rather than the peer pressure. Since students live on campus and are subject to the same rules on behaviour at home as they are at school, many of the discipline issues that plague schools today are resolved.

Why indiscipline in School?

It is important to emphasise that indiscipline is not tolerated in any school. Indiscipline in schools is the breaking of school regulations; it is the exact opposite of discipline. There are several ways to spot indifference in schools, including both within and outside of the classroom. Among these infractions are: Unfitting attire Being late Misconduct, harassment, vandalism, destruction of property, drug usage, and other immoral activities Since the student behaviour policy is the cornerstone of quality instruction in schools, it is imperative that the causes of indiscipline be examined and investigated. The root cause of indiscipline in schools, according to Ajah (2020), include: bad study habits, restless and inattention, inadequate home upbringing, abuse of seniority by prefects, low self-concept due to continuous negative labelling, etc.

Benefits of Curbing Indiscipline in Schools

A youngster who lacks discipline will never be able to carry out his ideas in real life, which will end up costing him a great deal in the long run. Students will be free to do whatever in a school where there is no discipline. Everyone is going to skip class. As a result, nobody will like taking lessons in a classroom. Additionally, the pupils won't be doing their schoolwork. In the end, there will be nothing for the kids to learn. Thus, maintaining order is crucial to fostering a learning atmosphere in the classroom.

- **It develops the students into strong individuals**
- Setting boundaries for the kids via discipline helps them understand right from wrong. The pupils' character is strengthened as a result, and they become strong and independent. Even pupils' analytical skills are developed via discipline. when a result, when infants get older, they may use their abilities to overcome obstacles in the actual world.
- **It gives them a teaching of a lifetime**
- Children can be shaped in any manner while they are still developing. They will adhere to discipline for the rest of their lives if they start practicing it at this age. A youngster acquires discipline at school, and he keeps this skill throughout his life. Students who understand the value of discipline adhere to it in the classroom and eventually develop a habit of it.
- **It leads to the social development of a child**
- Along with appreciating the boundaries of the connection, discipline helps pupils form closer ties with one another, with teachers, with parents, and so on. For instance, a youngster is aware of his relationship with his instructor and the boundaries of appropriate behaviour while they are together.

Guidance and Counseling as an Instrument for Curbing Indiscipline among Students

The use of experienced counsellors in schools who support instructors in instilling discipline in the kids can help reduce student indiscipline via counselling and guidance;

Orientation Service: Students who are new to the school as well as those who are starting a new course are both eligible for the orientation program. It is common knowledge that the students who enrol for the first time. Individuals who are promoted to higher grades in the school or come from

diverse origins in terms of family, socioeconomic level, geography, and aptitudes, talents, and abilities, are heterogeneous in nature. Therefore, the purpose of the orientation service is often to provide students with a thorough understanding of the school, as well as information about courses, policies, procedures, and various resources provided by the institution. In keeping with this, the school also maintains files on each student's biographical information, which includes identity, socioeconomic status, skills and aptitudes, course interests, and more.

Information Service: In fact, information is a key component of any guiding program. because it helps students make the right choices when it comes to planning their education, careers, and occupational paths. Simultaneously, it is advantageous for pupils to be able to adapt well to various social contexts, such as classroom and workplace settings.

Counselling Service: Counselling services are an essential component of guidance programs and are widely used in a variety of social settings, including families, schools, hospitals, and other counselling institutions. To help them overcome the issues that often arise in their life, parents may offer counselling to their children, instructors can help students in the classroom, physicians can help patients in the medical field, and so on. Thousands of issues that arise in daily life impede the growth and success of the individual because they are social, professional, and educational in character.

In today's dynamic society, seeking professional guidance is essential to finding answers to a plethora of issues, including changing one's dislike for a subject, issues with study habits, exam preparation, insufficient involvement in extracurricular and academic activities, free studentships, scholarships, and stipends, future career planning, forming and maintaining friendships, cooperating with teachers and peers, interacting with family and parents, handling romantic relationships, developing inferiority complex, behavioural issues, health issues, financial difficulties, issues with manners and morality, issues pertaining to leisure time utilisation, issues with underachievement, absenteeism, and dropping out.

Placement Service: Similar to other forms of guidance services, placement services are specifically provided by teachers or guidance workers to help students determine their own position in the educational system and the workforce while taking into account their aptitudes, interests, abilities, and attitudes. It is clear that each person visits the temple for learning with certain professional and vocational objectives in mind. Students can make informed decisions on educational courses, vocational courses, and trainings with the help of educational and vocational counsel. Both forms of assistance help students get suitable jobs and are designed to maximise their employment happiness.

Referral Service: The referral service is intended for students who are not receiving assistance and counselling from instructors or guidance counsellors in a typical group setting. The goal of this referral service is to connect people with specialists. Teachers and counsellors advise students in these unique situations to seek out specialised assistance from a person or organisation. Because the learner need careful attention and specialised assistance to solve the issues. The student is recommended to seek out better guidance services from a specialised person or agency, with consideration for the student's growth, by the teacher and guidance professional. However, teachers and guidance counsellors have an obligation to not only recommend students, but also to follow up with them to find out about their success and development in relation to the original goal of the referral. Thus, it makes sense for the teacher or guidance counsellor to maintain positive relationships with both the student and the referral organisations, which will enable the referral service's primary goal to be achieved.

Remedial Service: Remedial services, like referral services, are specialised services designed for children who are exceptional. Examples of these students include those who have speech abnormalities, hearing impairments, difficulty reading, difficulty forming study habits, etc. These remarkable kids aren't your typical kids who can read, think, and behave appropriately. Thus, in order to overcome these disabilities, individuals require specialised care. Teachers and counsellors set up remedial assistance for these extraordinary kids because of this. In general, the school offers it carefully. For this reason, nearly all students benefit from specific instruction, such as that intended to improve study skills. Remedial services are also a specific plan for the kids who are extraordinary. In the event of voice articulation, a low-cost tape recorder equipment may be arranged. In order to aid youngsters who have hearing issues and are easily handicapped in solving their problems, extra

assistance and efforts should be done. The primary goal of remedial services may be readily accomplished if instructors and counsellors make extra, sincere efforts for the welfare and well-being of the underprivileged children.

Follow-Up Service: The purpose of follow-up services, which are regarded as crucial guidance services, is to assess and determine the student's performance and advancement within the framework of their educational career, activities, and job placement. In addition to their primary responsibility of placing students in schools and finding jobs through placement services, teachers and guidance counsellors also have the crucial responsibility of assessing their students' progress and performance in their respective fields.

The role of the guidance counsellor is crucial in preventing student misconduct and preserving a welcoming, safe school environment that values diversity. Since punishing and disciplining pupils might jeopardise the therapeutic relationship, the therapist does not do so. Guidance counsellors can help reduce school indiscipline even further by:

- a. Working together with school stakeholders to create, implement, and uphold a developmentally appropriate school-wide discipline program
- b. Consulting with families, teachers, administrators, and other school personnel to understand developmentally appropriate student behaviour and promote positive student behaviour.
- c. Organising and leading initiatives (such as peer support, mentorship, conflict resolution, and anger management programs) to help students learn pro-social behaviour
- d. Supervising one-on-one and small-group therapy sessions that motivate kids to adopt positive behaviours and take ownership of their actions
- e. Educating staff members on classroom management, student behaviour, and discipline techniques such trauma-sensitive methods, (Reinbergs & Fefer, 2018)

CONCLUSION

The study comes to the conclusion that guidance and counselling services are crucial for improving kids' social and emotional adjustment, discipline, and overall school performance. Additionally, guidance and counselling departments assist in encouraging positive conduct in secondary school pupils. Furthermore, based on the results, guidance and counselling programs in secondary schools are essential for changing students' conduct by helping them manage their emotions, such as fear and anger, and fostering a peaceful environment in which they can learn. Thus, Zunker (2020) highlights the need for regular and intense guidance counselling services in secondary schools to address students' antisocial and indiscipline behaviour. characterised by arguments, rage, terror, and the potential for significant property damage and the death of innocent people. Academic success of pupils in Rivers State is influenced by guidance and counselling programs. The rate at which secondary school students transfer into postsecondary schools is also influenced by guidance and counselling services.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions were made:

1. The Ministry of Education should support guidance and counselling professionals in all public schools by strengthening their roles, facilitating their training, and giving them the tools they need to do their jobs well.
2. Nigeria Education Service ought to implement professional advice and counselling in senior schools.
3. Limited teaching periods should be assigned to guidance and counselling professionals in order to allow them ample opportunity to offer guidance services to students in need of their assistance.
4. School administrators should raise awareness about the value of guidance and counselling programs in the school in order to provide professional counsellors with the assistance they need.

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